

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of various Dialkyl Sulphoxides by Cerium(IV) in Acid Medium

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Solvent extraction of various metal ions using dialkyl sulphoxides as extractants has been reported¹. Extraction of americium(III) and neptunium(IV) from nitric acid solution is poor at higher acid concentration probably due to the oxidation of sulphoxides to sulphones. It is pertinent therefore to explore the *in situ* mechanism involved in the oxidation process, in order to improve the extraction efficiency. Though much study on the oxidation of lower members of alkyl sulphoxides has been reported^{2,3}, higher members of the family have not received much attention. The present study relates to the mechanism of oxidation of DMSO, DPSO and DDSO with Ce^{IV} in acetic acid medium, in order to ascertain the effect of carbon chain-length on the process and the mechanism involved therein.

Results and Discussion

The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_1) increases with increasing [substrate], whereas the second order rate constant, $k_2 = k_1/[substrate]$ remains almost constant in all cases (Table 1), indicating overall first order dependence on both [substrate] as well as [oxidant]. k_1 also increases with increasing carbon chain-length of the sulphoxides, i.e. DDSO > DPSO > DMSO (Table 2). The increasing concentration of acetic acid (7.65–8.50 M) does not affect the rate of reaction in case of DDSO but facilitates the same in DMSO and DPSO (Table 3), which agrees with the data reported earlier⁴. The experiment has been undertaken at a given concentration of HOAc (i.e. 7.65 M) at different temperatures and the data are incorporated in Table 4. In all cases, induced polymerisation of acrylamide is observed during oxidation, exploring that irrespective of the carbon chain-length, the reaction proceeds by a free radical mechanism, in conformity with the literature⁵.

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TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF VELOCITY CONSTANT ON [SUBSTRATE]

[Ce^{IV}] = 1.0 × 10⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 3.5, [HOAc] = 7.65 mol dm⁻³,
Temp = 308 K

[Substrate] 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	k_1 (10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)		
	DMSO	DPSO	DDSO
0.5	0.50	0.7	1.1
0.75	0.80	1.1	1.5
1.0	0.95	1.4	2.1
1.5	1.40	1.9	3.2

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF VELOCITY CONSTANT ON [OXIDANT]

[R₂SO] = 0.5 × 10⁻², [H₂SO₄] = 3.5, [HOAc] = 7.65 mol dm⁻³,
Temp = 300 K

[Oxidant] 10 ³ dm ⁻³	k_1 (10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)		
	DMSO	DPSO	DDSO
0.5	0.53	0.72	1.0
1.0	0.50	0.70	1.1
1.5	0.49	0.71	1.0

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON VELOCITY CONSTANT

[Sulphoxide] = 1.5 × 10⁻², [Ce^{IV}] = 1.0 × 10⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 3.5 mol dm⁻³; Temp = 308 K

[HOAc] mol dm ⁻³	k_1 (10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)		
	DMSO	DPSO	DDSO
7.65	1.4	1.9	3.2
8.05	1.8	2.1	3.2
8.50	2.0	3.2	3.3

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF ALKYL SULPHOXIDES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

[Ce^{IV}] = 1.0 × 10⁻³, [R₂SO] = 1.5 × 10⁻², [H₂SO₄] = 3.5,
[HOAc] = 7.65 mol dm⁻³

Substrate	k ₂ (10 ² dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH [‡]	-ΔS [‡]
	308.0 K	313.0 K	318.0 K	323.0 K		
DMSO	0.95	1.5	2.3	3.7	75.8±2	76.3±6
DPSO	1.30	2.3	3.3	5.0	67.8±4	98.4±11
DDSO	2.10	3.2	4.4	5.8	54.9±3	141.2±12

ΔH in kJ mol⁻¹; ΔS in JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

Mechanism of oxidation : A perusal of literature⁶⁻⁸ on Ce^{IV} oxidation in H₂SO₄ shows complex formation with sulphate ion, viz. Ce(SO₄)²⁺, Ce(SO₄)₂ and Ce(SO₄)₃⁻ species. Some equilibria involving HCe(SO₄)₄³⁻, H₂Ce(SO₄)₄²⁻, H₃Ce(SO₄)₄⁻ ions and H₄Ce(SO₄)₄ have also been suggested^{6,7} to explain the mechanism of certain reactions. But under the present experimental conditions, the active oxidant species⁷, are Ce(SO₄)²⁺, Ce(SO₄)₂ or higher sulphato complexes. On the basis of the results the possible mechanism is

where Ce^{IV} denotes the reactive species Ce(SO₄)₂, Ce(SO₄)²⁺ or other sulphato complexes. For the reaction scheme, the rate law will take the form,

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}}{dt} &= \frac{2k_1k_2f_1[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{substrate}]}{k_{-1} + k_2} \\
 &= k[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{substrate}]
 \end{aligned}$$

where, $k = \frac{2k_1k_2f_1}{k_{-1} + k_2}$
($f_1 \leq 1$)

The concentration of reactive [Ce^{IV}] species = f_1 [Ce^{IV}]_T, f_1 being the fraction defined by various equilibrium constants^{8,9} for sulphato Ce^{IV} species which controls the concentration of active Ce^{IV} species in H₂SO₄ media. As the reaction has been carried out at a given concentration of H₂SO₄, f_1 is constant under the present experimental condition, hence a pseudo-first order condition is maintained throughout.

Activation parameters : The activation parameters are calculated from Eyring plots by using simplified Eyring equation,

$$\log \frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{T} = (-\Delta H^{\ddagger} / 2.303R) / T + 10.318 + \Delta S^{\ddagger} / 2.303R$$

where, ΔH, ΔS and R stand for activation enthalpy, activation entropy and gas constant respectively. In order to explore the role of different alkyl groups on the oxidation of sulphoxides, activation parameters are computed (Table 4). It is evident from the data that with increasing carbon chain-length of the sulphoxides, the activation entropy increases appreciably suggesting that complex formation is more favourable in the latter case leading to higher rate of oxidation, which agrees with the present observation. Other contributing factors responsible for enhancing the rate is the inductive effect of various alkyl groups on >S=O group, to generate the radical species in the rate-determining step.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Double-distilled water was used. Acetic acid (99.9%) was used as solvent. DMSO (B.D.H.) was distilled over CaO under reduced pressure. Dipentyl and didecyl sulphoxides were synthesised¹⁰ purified by recrystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and characterised (m.p., tlc and ir).

Kinetics measurements : The experiment was carried out in the temperature range 308.0–328.0 K, varying the concentration of the substrate, oxidant as well as solvent.

The rate measurements were made under pseudo-first order conditions using $[R_2SO] = (1.0-3.0) \times 10^{-2}$ and $[Ce^{IV}] = (1.0-3.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Solution of R_2SO (R = methy, pentyl and decyl) in acetic acid (15.3 M) and Ce^{IV} in 7.0 M H_2SO_4 were equilibrated separately at the desired temperature and mixed. The course of the reaction was followed by withdrawing a known volume (5.0 cm³) of the reaction mixture at definite intervals of time and pouring into known excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution. The unreacted Fe^{II} was titrated against standard potassium dichromate solution using barium diphenyl amine sulphonate as indicator³. The rate constants, obtained from duplicate measurements, agreed within $\pm 5\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The products isolated from the reaction mixture after 24 h (~ 90%), by extracting with crushed ice, were washed with distilled water and recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60°–80°). The crystals obtained were chromatographed using tlc. Authentic samples of DMSO, DPSO and DDSO and their sulphones were also subjected to tlc for comparison. The spots were identified by exposure to iodine and the solvent system employed were benzene-ethanol (80 : 20, v/v) mixture. The R_f values obtained were same as those of known samples of sulphoxides. The runs undertaken in the presence of excess Ce^{IV} in 3.5 M H_2SO_4 at 35° indicate that 2 moles of oxidant react with 1 mole of substrate in the process as

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